

iJEResearch

International Journal of Education and Research

Vol. 1, Number 3, December - 2025 | Peer-Reviewed Journal

ISSN 2764-9733 | ijerresearch.org

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18095110

PHARMACEUTICAL CARE IN PUBLIC HEALTH

AUTHOR

Priscila Souza da Costa: Master's student in Public Health at Universidad UNIDA, Administrator and Entrepreneur, Pharmacist with a postgraduate degree in Clinical Analysis.

Contact: priscilla_lbn@hotmail.com | +55(92)99416-0180

ABSTRACT

Pharmaceutical care is patient-centered and is a practice that aims to ensure the correct and effective use of medications, improving the patient's quality of life by promoting health and helping to prevent disease. The practice of pharmaceutical care is a tool that facilitates interaction between pharmacists and users of the healthcare system.

Keywords: Pharmaceutical care. Public health. Rational use of medicines. Quality of life.